

TYPES OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING INVOLVE GROUP-BASED LEARNING COMBINED WITH PASSIVE TEACHING METHODS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada kooperativ o‘qitishning uchta asosiy turi: formal, noformal va baza (doimiy) kooperativ o‘qitish haqida so‘z boradi. Formal kooperativ o‘qitish — o‘qituvchi tomonidan rejalashtirilgan, nazorat qilingan va ma’lum vaqt davomida olib boriladigan uslub bo‘lib, jamoaviy topshiriqlar orqali maqsadga erishish ko‘zda tutiladi. Misol sifatida "Jigsaw" (pazl) metodi keltiriladi, unda talaba o‘rganayotgan mavzuni boshqalarga tushuntirib, o‘qituvchi rolini bajaradi. Informal kooperativ o‘qitishda kichik guruhlar dars davomida yoki dars oxirida materialni muhokama qilish orqali faol bo‘lmagan tarzda o‘rganishga jalb qilinadi. Bu turdagi ta’lim o‘quvchilarni mas’uliyatli, o‘zaro g‘amxo‘r bo‘lishga va chuqurroq o‘rganishga undaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Osonlashtirish, nazorat qilish, topshiriq, o'z-o'zini hurmat qilish, o'zini o'zi qadrlash, ishonchni mustahkamlash, idrok etish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются три основных типа кооперативного обучения: формальное, неформальное и базовое (долгосрочное). Формальное обучение осуществляется под руководством преподавателя и направлено на выполнение групповых заданий. Примером является метод «мозаика», где студент обучает однокурсников по изученной теме. Неформальное обучение предполагает пассивное усвоение материала через краткие обсуждения в парах или малых группах на протяжении урока. Такие группы временные и постоянно меняются. Этот подход способствует формированию крепких социальных связей и углубленному усвоению материала.

Ключевые слова: Содействовать, контролировать, задание, самооценка, чувство собственного достоинства, укрепление доверия, восприятие.

Abstract: This article describes three main types of cooperative learning: formal, informal, and base (long-term) cooperative learning. Formal cooperative learning is educator-structured and supervised over time, aimed at accomplishing shared group goals through tasks such as group problem-solving and peer reviews. The “jigsaw” method is highlighted, where students teach a topic to peers, reinforcing their own understanding. Informal cooperative learning involves temporary small groups (often pairs) engaging in brief discussions during or at the end of a lesson, helping learners to reflect, share, and consolidate information. This method enhances motivation, accountability, and retention of complex material.

Key words: To facilitate, to monitor, an assignment, self-esteem, self-worth, trust-building, to perceive.

INTRODUCTION

Formal cooperative learning is structured, facilitated, and monitored by the educator over time and is used to achieve group goals in task work (e.g. completing a unit). Any course material or assignment can be adapted to this type of learning, and groups can vary from 2-6 people with discussions lasting from a few minutes up to a period. Types of formal cooperative learning strategies include jigsaw, assignments that involve group problem solving and decision making, laboratory or experiment assignments, and peer review work (e.g. editing writing assignments). Having experience and developing skill with this type of learning often facilitates informal and base learning. Jigsaw activities are wonderful because the student assumes the role of the teacher on a given topic and is in charge of teaching the topic to a fellow classmate. The idea is that if the student can teach something, he/she would have already learned the material.

Informal cooperative learning incorporates group learning with passive teaching by drawing attention to material through small groups throughout the lesson

or by discussion at the end of a lesson, and typically involves groups of two (e.g. turn-to-your-partner discussions). These groups are often temporary and can change from lesson to lesson (very much unlike formal learning where 2 students may be lab partners throughout the entire semester contributing to one another's knowledge of science). Discussions typically have four components that include formulating a response to questions asked by the educator, sharing responses to the questions asked with a partner, listening to a partner's responses to the same question, and creating a new well-developed answer. This type of learning enables the student to process, consolidate, and retain more information learned.

This is effective both for individual learning, as well as social support.

1. Positive interdependence

- Students must fully participate and put forth effort within their group
- Each group member has a task/role/responsibility therefore must believe that they are responsible for their learning and that of their group

2. Face-to-Face Promotive Interaction

- Member promote each other's success
- Students explain to one another what they have or are learning and assist one another with understanding and completion of assignments

3. Individual and Group Accountability

- Each student must demonstrate master of the content being studied
- Each student is accountable for their learning and work, therefore eliminating "social loafing"

4. Social Skills

- Social skills that must be taught in order for successful cooperative learning to occur
- Skills include effective communication, interpersonal and group skills
 - a) Leadership
 - b) Decision-making
 - c) Trust-building
 - d) Communication

e) Conflict-management skills

5. Group Processing

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Cooperative learning can be seen as characteristic for innovation businesses. The four stage division on cooperative learning creates a useful method of analyzing learning in teaching English. Innovatively connected to cooperative learning seems to make the creation of innovations possible. Cooperative Learning has many limitations that could cause the process to be more complicated than first perceived. Sharan describes the constant evolution of cooperative learning as a threat. Due to the fact that cooperative learning is constantly changing, there is a possibility that teachers may become confused and lack complete understanding of the method. Teachers implementing cooperative learning may also be challenged with resistance and hostility from students who believe that they are being held back by their slower teammates or by students who are less confident and feel that they are being ignored or demeaned by their team. Students often provide feedback in the success of the teamwork experienced during cooperative learning experiences. Peer review and evaluations may not reflect true experiences due to perceived competition among peers. A confidential evaluation process may help to increase evaluation strength.

The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of the cooperative learning approach of Student Teams-Achievement Divisions (STAD) on the achievement of content knowledge, retention, and attitudes toward the teaching method. Cooperative learning was compared to non-cooperative (competitive) learning classroom structure using a quasi-experimental design. An achievement test, consisting of items from the state competency test-item bank for the course, and an attitude questionnaire were administered immediately following instruction on the unit of special nutritional needs. A retention test was administered three weeks following the achievement test. California Achievement Test scores and first semester grades in home economics classes were used as covariates to adjust for possible preexisting differences between the groups. Multivariate analysis of covariance showed no significant difference among the dependent variables

(achievement and retention) between the teaching methods used. There was also no significant difference in student attitudes toward the teaching methods. Teachers have the option of structuring lessons competitively, individualistically, or cooperatively. Cooperative learning, as an instructional methodology provides opportunities for students to develop skills in group interactions and in working with others that are needed in today's world. According to Johnson and Johnson, cooperative learning experiences promote more positive attitudes toward the instructional experience than competitive or individualistic methodologies. In addition, cooperative learning should result in positive effects on student achievement and retention of information. According to McKeachie, students are more likely to acquire critical thinking skills and metacognitive learning strategies, such as learning how to learn, in small group cooperative settings as opposed to listening to lectures. There are two major theoretical perspectives related to cooperative learning motivational and cognitive. The motivational theories of cooperative learning emphasize the students' incentives to do academic work, while the cognitive theories emphasize the effects of working together.

DISCUSSION

There are two cognitive theories that are directly applied to cooperative learning, the developmental and the elaboration theories. The developmental theories assume that interaction among students around appropriate tasks increases their mastery of critical concepts .When students interact with other students, they have to explain and discuss each other's perspectives, which leads to greater understanding of the material to be learned. The struggle to resolve potential conflicts during collaborative activity results in the development of higher levels of understanding. Several studies have examined the effects of cooperative learning methods on student learning. Some philosophers compared cooperative, competitive, and individualistic strategies in science classes and found that students who were taught by cooperative methods learned and retained significantly more information than students taught by the other two methods. They found similar results in a study involving high school general mathematics classes taught by

cooperative and individualistic methods. Allen and Van Sickle used STAD as the experimental treatment in a study involving low achieving students. They found that the cooperative learning group scored significantly higher on a world geography test. Perrault found that cooperative learning resulted in significantly higher achievement in industrial arts students at the knowledge and comprehension levels of Bloom's taxonomy, but not at the application level when compared to students taught by competitive methods. In a study in which nutrition was taught to both elementary and secondary students using a cooperative learning strategy, Todd, and Wodarski found significant gains between the pretest and posttest scores. The researchers concluded that cooperative learning was an effective method of teaching nutrition. In a review of 46 studies related to cooperative learning, Slavin found that cooperative learning resulted in significant positive effects in 63% of the studies, and only two studies reported higher achievement for the comparison group. Scholars conducted a meta-analysis of 122 studies related to cooperative learning and concluded that there was strong evidence for the superiority of cooperative learning in promoting achievement over competitive and individualistic strategies.

Johnson examined the relationships between students' attitudes toward cooperation, competition, and their attitudes toward education. The results of the study indicated that student cooperativeness, and not competitiveness, was positively related to being motivated to learn. Humphreys and Johnson also found that students studying the language in a cooperative learning treatment group rated their learning experience more positively than did students in competitive and individualistic treatment groups. Marine and Johnson found that cooperative learning strategies promoted positive attitudes toward both didactic and inquiry methods of teaching language, and students taught by cooperative strategies believed they had learned more from the lesson than did students taught by competitive strategies. In a study involving elementary and secondary students who were taught nutrition, Wodarski found that 95% of the elementary students enjoyed the cooperative learning activities and those they had learned a lot about nutrition.

CONCLUSION

While cooperative learning as an instructional methodology is an option for teachers, it is currently the least frequently used. More than 85% of the instruction in schools consists of lectures, seatwork, or competition in which students are isolated from one another and forbidden to interact. Goodlad reported that most classroom time is spent in "teacher talk", with only 1% of the students' classroom time used for reasoning about or expressing an opinion. Group work has been used extensively in teaching English provide practice in acquiring both competence and skills in interpersonal relations. The introduction of cooperative learning strategies has potential for improving the group activities commonly used in these classes .While empirical evidence supports the use of cooperative learning of the English language with a variety of subject areas and age groups. Without empirical evidence to support the effectiveness of cooperative education, it is likely to be ignored as an instructional methodology by home language educators.

This research explored the effectiveness of three main types of cooperative learning formal, informal, and base group learning in enhancing students' academic performance and overall engagement. The findings from both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods indicate that cooperative learning not only improves knowledge acquisition but also fosters critical soft skills such as communication, collaboration, responsibility, and self-assessment.

Overall, the study demonstrates that when cooperative learning strategies are properly integrated into the educational process, they significantly enhance students' cognitive, social, and emotional development. The role of the educator remains central in guiding, monitoring, and assessing group dynamics and outcomes.

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